

transplanted irrigated rice during 1987 wet season (kharif).

Soil was red sandy loam (Alfisols), with pH 6.7, 0.031% available N, 10.9 kg available P/ha, 171 kg K/ha, and cation exchange capacity of 12.6 meq/100 g. Rice varieties were Rasi (120 d) and Mandya Vijaya (145 d).

LGU was applied by broadcasting on drained soil. Prilled urea (PU) was applied according to recommended practice in the area (50% broadcast and incorporated 3-4 h before planting, 25% broadcast without incorporation at tillering, and 25% broadcast at panicle initiation).

Ammonia volatilization loss was measured in the field by direct trapping procedure and leaching loss was measured by periodically inserting leaching tubes (with microporous ceramic base) below the rooting zone, 30 cm deep to collect leachate for determining ammoniacal and nitrate N. Cumulative loss of ammoniacal N and nitrate N was computed on the basis of

Rice yield as affected by LSU/LGU.

Treatment ^a	Grain yield (t/ha)		Total N uptake (kg/ha) in grain + straw		Cumulative loss of Fertilizer N ^b (kg/ha)
	Rasi	Mandya Vijaya	Rasi	Mandya Vijaya	
Control, no N	2.0	3.7	43	56	—
LSU/LGU, all basal	4.8	5.3	94	126	24
PU in 3 splits (recommended practice of 50-25-25 at planting, tillering, PI)	4.5	5.4	95	112	28
LSU/LGU in 2 splits (66-34 at planting and tillering)	5.1	5.8	136	129	20
LSU/LGU in 3 splits (50-25-25 at planting, tillering, PI)	4.9	5.5	105	117	19
LSD (0.05)	0.3	0.3			
CV (%)	7.5	7.5			

^aN rate is 100 kg N/ha. All treatments received 22 kg P and 41 kg K/ha. ^b Through volatilization and leaching.

percolation loss of water using drum culture technique.

Application of LSU/ LGU in two splits increased yield significantly in both varieties (see table). This appeared to be due mainly to better uptake of N by the plant and lower loss of fertilizer

N through volatilization and leaching. Three splits of LSU/LGU did not show any advantage over two splits. LSU/ LGU applied all basal did not show any significant reduction in yield from PU applied in three splits. □

Synergistic effect of organic manure and N fertilizer on irrigated rice

T. Hussain and G. Jilani, Soil Science Department, University of Agriculture, Faisalabad, Pakistan

We evaluated the efficiency of N source and method of application in irrigated rice KS-282 in a field experiment.

Soil was Typic Camborthids, sandy clay loam in texture having pH 7.9, ECe

0.70 dS/m and CEC 7.8 mmol (I)/ 100 g. Organic matter was 0.52%; N content 0.04%. Plot size was 16 m² and plant spacing 20 × 20 cm in a randomized complete block design with 4 replications. All plots received 40 kg PK/ha.

Urea supergranules (USG) and prilled urea (PU) were compared with *S. aculeata* and *S. rostrata* as green manure and barnyard manure (BM) in combination with PU. N rate was 87 kg/ ha for each source.

USG was superior in all respects (see table). *S. rostrata* + PU was statistically equivalent to USG. Growth and yield of rice were low with *S. aculeata* + PU, and BM + PU compared to PU alone, but N recovery from PU alone was the lowest of all sources. □

Effect of organic manure and N fertilizer on growth and yield of irrigated rice.^a

Treatment ^b	Plant height (cm)	Tillers/m ²	Grain (t/ha)	Straw (t/ha)	Agronomic efficiency (kg rice/kg N)	N recovery (%)
Control(no N)	80 c	239 d	3.7 c	4.4 e	—	—
USG	95 a	340 a	5.7 a	7.8 a	23.1	54
PU	87 b	266 cd	5.3 b	7.0 c	18.4	46
<i>S. aculeata</i> + PU	86 b	298 bc	5.2 b	6.5 d	17.2	48
<i>S. rostrata</i> + PU	89 b	307 ab	5.6 a	7.3 b	21.5	52
Barnyard manure + PU	88 b	261 d	5.1 b	7.1 bc	16.7	48
SE	2	11	0.06	0.08		

^aIn a column, any 2 means followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5% level by LSD test. ^b N source applied at 40 kg N/ha.

Effect of zincated diammonium phosphate (Zn-DAP) on rainfed lowland rice

R. Ilangovan and S. Palaniappan, Agronomy Department, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University (TNAU), Coimbatore 641003, Tamil Nadu, India

We studied the effect of different grades of Zn-DAP on grain yield of IR50 in wet season (kharif) 1985 and summer 1986. Soils were clay loam with pH 7.5 and 7.9, low DTPA-Zn (0.7 and 1.1 ppm) and organic C (0.21 and 0.34%), low available N (234.5 and 210.6 kg/ha), and high available P (38.5 and 40 kg/ha) and K (325.6 and 316.9 kg/ha).

The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with three replications. Subplot treatments were grades of Zn-DAP (1-6%) applied before transplanting; ZnSO₄ soil application (25 kg/ha); ZnSO₄ foliar application (0.5% sprayed 30 and 45 d after transplanting); seedling roots dipped in 2% ZnO suspension; and no Zn (control). Main plots were with and without green manure at 12.5 t/ha (sunn hemp *Crotalaria juncea* L. in wet season and pongam leaves *Pongamia glabra* Vent. in summer). All plots received 100-21.9-41.5 kg NPK/ha.

Zn application significantly increased grain yield (see table); 6% Zn-DAP was both efficient and economical. □

Effect of Zn-DAP on grain yield of rainfed lowland rice.

Treatment	1985 wet season yield (t/ha)		1986 summer yield (t/ha)		Zn added (kg/ha)
	With GM	No GM	With GM	No GM	
No Zn-SSP	5.2	5.1	5.3	5.1	—
1% Zn-DAP	5.9	5.7	5.7	5.6	1.1
2% Zn-DAP	6.0	5.8	6.4	5.5	2.2
3% Zn-DAP	6.1	5.9	6.7	6.0	3.4
4% Zn-DAP	6.2	5.9	6.6	5.7	4.6
5% Zn-DAP	6.2	5.9	6.8	6.2	5.8
6% Zn-DAP	6.4	6.0	6.7	6.5	7.1
ZnSO ₄ - basal	6.1	5.7	6.5	5.7	5.8
ZnSO ₄ - foliar	5.9	5.7	6.1	5.9	—
ZnO root dip	6.2	5.4	6.2	5.6	—
No Zn-DAP	—	—	5.6	5.1	—
LSD (0.05)					
Green manure (GM)		ns		ns	
Zn treatments		0.5		0.6	
GM × Zn		ns		ns	
Zn × GM		ns		ns	

Efficiency of prilled urea (PU) and urea supergranules (USG) in rapidly percolating soil

R. S. Rekhi and M. S. Bajwa, Punjab Agricultural University (PAU), Ludhiana, India; and J. L. Starr, USDA-ARS, Beltsville, Maryland 20705, USA

We studied the fate and efficiency of PU and USG in rice grown on a rapidly percolating loamy sand at PAU farm. Soil was a Typic Ustochrept, CEC 4.5 meq/100 g, pH 8.2, 0.3% organic C, 0.06% total N, with an N mineralization rate of 16 mg N/kg soil after 7 d anaerobic incubation at 40 °C.

N was applied at 0, 37.5, 75.0, and 112.5 kg N/ha in plots measuring 4.8 × 4.8 m. In the plots with 75.0 kg N/ha, ¹⁵N-labeled PU and USG with 5 atom percent excess ¹⁵N were applied in rectangular metal frame microplots (1.2 × 0.8 × 0.3 m) within the main plots. PU was applied in 3 equal splits at transplanting, active tillering, and panicle initiation; USG was placed 8-10 cm deep in the center of 4 rice hills in alternate rows. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications.

Rice variety PR106 was transplanted the last week of Jun, 35 d after seeding, and harvested the last week of Oct. Grain and straw samples were analyzed

Effect of N source and level on growth, yield, and N uptake of rice.

Treatment	Plant ht (m)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Yield (t/ha)		N uptake (kg/ha)		Apparent recovery (%)
			Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw	
Control	84	232	3.7	4.5	36	11	—
PU 37.5	89	297	5.0	6.0	49	18	55
PU 75.0	96	308	5.7	7.3	57	25	48
PU 112.5	101	391	7.0	7.4	77	24	48
USG 37.5	82	255	3.7	4.1	37	12	4
USG 75.0	94	285	4.4	5.5	43	14	14
USG 112.5	91	267	4.8	4.7	45	13	10
LSD (0.05)	7	33	0.7	2.1	9	7	—

Balance of ¹⁵N-labeled fertilizer in rice.

for total N content and N uptake. Soil was destructively sampled at harvest with a rectangular soil sampler (30 × 13.3 × 50 cm) for total Kjeldahl N and ¹⁵N analyses.

Plant height, number of panicles, yield, and N uptake showed that PU was significantly superior to USG (see table). Apparent recovery of N was higher with PU (48-55%) than with